

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Training Platform, Work Package 2 -
 Consolidating the Training Platform Infrastructure

M2.11 Maintain, support and update the ELIXIR Lesson Template

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

In the past, there was no standard way of creating and maintaining training materials within ELIXIR. However, choices made during the design stage can have a large effect on how training materials are disseminated and reused. In this milestone, we aim to provide a technical infrastructure in the form of a lesson template to support ELIXIR training material developers. This lesson template serves as a starting point for making standardized, reproducible and FAIR training materials within ELIXIR. The template consists of a git repository with a backbone for creating a visually appealing website in the ELIXIR look-and-feel. It is richly documented and supports: bioschemas annotation, code chunks, file downloads (e.g. pdfs), citation, authorship information and many more features.

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Supporting Documents

Lesson template:

<https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/ELIXIR-TrP-LessonTemplate-MkDocs>

Lesson template instructions:

<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-TrP-LessonTemplateInstructions-MkDocs/>

Dissemination Plans

The lesson template is currently published on GitHub and Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/7913092>, and on SPLASH

(<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/elixir-lesson-template>). As

it is part of other milestones and deliverables within the work package, further dissemination will follow during current and future work, e.g. in M2.10 (Establish a process of recognition for contribution to lesson templates), D2.5 (Documentation outlining the governance and maintenance structure for the Training GitHub organisation) and D2.6 (Documentation outlining the standard operating procedures for the Training Lesson Template Maintainers).